

Development and Evaluation of Antibacterial Polyherbal Cream & Comparison with Marketed Product.

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Abstract: The sudden rise of the herbal cosmeceutical market due to growing awareness about harsh chemicals being incorporated into various products/formulations and increasing concern to look good over the long term is what inspired us to contribute a bit by formulating the most common day-to-day-used formulation. To reduce the adverse effect produced by synthetic formulation and also at the same time have equivalent or more efficacy of this formulation, an approach of using a combination of various plants has been applied in this study. The present study was commenced to evaluate the quantitative profiling and antimicrobial activity of cream prepared from extracts of traditional plants. The cup-plate agar diffusion method determined the anti-microbial activity against (*Escherichia coli* & *Bacillus subtilis*). To estimate the comparative effectiveness of the formulation the standard drugs were used as reference (Cloben - G).

Keywords: Polyherbal formulation, Cream, Anti-bacterial Activity, Soxhlet extraction, Neem, Nutmeg, Cinnamon.

I. Introduction

The term “Antibacterial” describes a substance/agent’s capacity to prevent the growth of or eradicate bacteria. Bacteria are single-celled germs that can infect and harm people, animals, and plants in several ways. Targeting specific bacterial structures or metabolic processes, antibacterial chemicals or agents stops the growth of bacteria or kills them. The invasion & colonization of pathogenic microbes into a host organism results in bacterial infections. Single-celled microbes known as bacteria can be found in a variety of habitats, including the human body. Many bacteria are benign or even helpful, but when they penetrate and multiply inside the body, illness or disorder can occur.

Fig. 1 Neem a few types of

Despite the many antibacterial medicines that are currently accessible, topical infections frequently arise and frequently offer treatment hurdles to doctors. The challenge of combating multidrug-resistant bacteria, viruses, and fungi may seem daunting, but let us not be discouraged. Instead, let us embrace this challenge as an opportunity to come up with innovative antibacterial techniques that can save lives and protect public health. Together, we can make a difference. Cold sores, nappy rashes, and tinea versicolor are a few common instances of topical skin infections. [1-3] [8] [11][14]

Fig. 1 Neem

A great emphasis has been placed on plant study in recent years, and evidence has been amassed to show the vast potential of medicinal plants used in various traditional systems. In terms of drug development, plant chemicals will be more effective than synthetic chemicals at a specific pharmacological target. Plant chemical components are thus one of the most important sources for the most important new drug discoveries. Therapeutic herbs used traditionally includes neem, cinnamon and nutmeg are renowned for their healing

Fig. 2 Nutmeg

abilities, and various sections of them have been employed by Indian traditional healers to cure a variety of illnesses. Neem, often referred to as margosa consists of all aerial parts of the plant known as *Azadirachta indica* which belongs to the meliaceae family. India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Malaysia, South Africa and East Africa are among the countries where it is present. The plant includes a significant amount of diterpenes (surgical and nimble), Triterpenes (β -sitosterol and stigmasterol) limonoids (maliantriol, nimbidine, azadiractin, nimbediol), and sulphurous compounds (rutin, kampferol, quercetin). Scientific studies have shown that neem contains a variety of compounds with antimicrobial, insecticide, and antifeedant effects. Spermicidal action can be found in neem oil. Because of Nimbin, neem has antibacterial activity.

The dried seed kernels of *Myristica fragrans*, a member of the myristicaceae family, are what make up nutmeg, also known as *Myristica* and *nux moschata*. It originated in the Molucca Island and now is grown in Indonesia, the Caribbean Island and other tropical nations. It is grown in Tamil Nadu and Kerala India. 5-16% volatile oil and roughly 30% fat are present in nutmeg. About 4-8% of volatile oil is made up of myristicin, eliminic acid, and safrole. About 60% of fixed oil's fatty acids are myristic followed by palmitic, oleic, lauric, and other acids. Nutmeg butter is another name for the spice's fat. As an aromatic, a stimulant, and a carminative, nutmeg is employed. Additionally, it serves as a flavoring agent. In the soap industry nutmeg butter also known as Banda soap is employed. In the treatment of rheumatism, nutmeg's volatile oil and fats are employed. According to a current study, nutmeg has anti-bacterial capabilities because it contains a chemical constituent called

Fig. 3 Cinnamon

pinene.[2-3][8]

Ceylon cinnamon often referred to as cinnamon bark, kalmidalchini and other names, consist of the inner bark of shoots of coppiced *Cinnamomum zylanicum* tree, which belongs to the Lauraceae family. The evergreen tree of the tropics known as cinnamon is thought to have originated in Sri Lanka and the Indian state of Malabar. Additionally, Brazil and Jamaica both have it. About 0.5 to 1 % of volatile oil, 1.2% of tannins (phlobatannins), mucilage, calcium oxalate, starch, and the sweetener mannitol are all found in cinnamon. The volatile oil contains 60-70% cinnamaldehyde, 5-10% eugenol, benzaldehyde, cuminaldehyde, and other terpenes including phellandrenes, pinene, cymene, caryophyllenes. [2-3][8-9][15-17]

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It is used as a moderate astringent, stomachic, and carminative. Additionally, it functions as a stimulant, an aromatic, an antimicrobial, and a flavoring agent. Cinnamon has an anti-bacterial effect since it contains the chemical compound known as cinnamaldehyde. Antibacterial creams are topical preparations with active chemicals created primarily to prevent the growth of bacteria on the skin's surface or to kill existing bacteria. Infections of the skin caused by bacteria such as those from cuts, wounds, burns, and specific skin conditions are frequently treated with them or prevented from occurring. The current study's goal was to create topical cream using neem, cinnamon and nutmeg extracts and test its antibacterial effectiveness against *Escherichia coli* & *Bacillus subtilis* in vitro.

II. Material & Method

A. Collection of Herbs

The plant powders of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), and Cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zylanicum* nees) were collected from the Purna shop, opposite Mahadev mandir, Tulsidham road, Bharuch. Powdered material was extracted with a suitable solvent. Nutmeg oil was collected from the local market of Bharuch. Both the powder was authenticated in the lab of Pharmacognosy lab at Laxminarayan dev college of Pharmacy.

Fig. 4 Steps to setup S

B. Extraction of Herbs

This involves the extraction of Neem & Cinnamon using the Soxhlet apparatus to get alcoholic extracts using ethanol as solvent. The procedure is given below:

For extraction of cinnamon, 100 gm cinnamon sticks were broken into smaller bits and put within a thick filter paper then into thimble before being inserted into the Soxhlet's main chamber. Ethanol was used as a solvent to carry out the extraction. The extraction was carried out till the thimble contained a clear solution. It was then filtered out and allowed to evaporate with the help of a water bath.

For extraction of neem, the main chamber of the Soxhlet extractor was loaded with a thimble in which a thick filter paper filled with 26 gm of neem powder is kept. 300 cc of methanol was used to carry out extraction that was carried out till the thimble collected clear solution (2 hours). The solution was filtered and allowed to evaporate by using

CINNAMALDEHYDE

C. Procedure

To formulate a cream, certain essential tools are required which include a pair of beakers, a glass rod, two water baths, two Bunsen burners, a weighing balance, a spatula, butter paper, and two thermometers. The following table shows the quantity taken for all the ingredients added to formulate a cream (For – 40 gm).

Fig. 5 Soxhlet apparatus

All the materials needed are weighed accurately. In the first beaker, propylene glycol, nutmeg oil, and beeswax were added. Then, for even mixing, heat on a water bath. A little while later, an oil phase developed. In a second beaker, ingredients such as cinnamon oil, neem oil, distilled water, glycerin, zinc oxide, methylcellulose, carboxymethylcellulose, and sodium benzoate were added. The aqueous phase was created by boiling all the components together in a water bath. A semisolid mass was created after adding the oil phase to the aqueous phase with constant stirring. [4-7][10-12]

Table 1: Ingredients with their quantity

Sr.no.	Ingredients	Quantity		Uses
		F1	F2	
1	Cinnamon extract	1 ml	1 ml	Antimicrobial Agent
2	Neem extract	1.5 ml	1.5 ml	Antimicrobial Agent
3	Nutmeg oil	0.8 ml	0.8 ml	Antimicrobial Agent
4	Bee's wax	1.2 gm	0.5 gm	Emulsifying Agent
7	Distilled water	25 ml	25 ml	Vehicle
9	Glycerine	1.3 ml	1 ml	Emollient
10	Methylcellulose	1.4 gm	2 gm	Stabilizer
11	Propylene glycol	1.5 ml	1 ml	Humectant
12	Carboxymethyl cellulose	3 gm	2 gm	Binding Agent
13	Zinc oxide	1.6 gm	0.8 gm	Photo protectant
14	Sodium Benzoate	1 gm	0.1 gm	Preservatives

D. Evaluations

The following criteria and clear instructions are used to evaluate the cream : .[4-7][10-12][19]

- 1) *Physical Evaluation*: Physical characteristics like colour, smell, consistency and state of formulation were used to further assess the formulation of our cream:

Color: Visual inspection of the cream was used to determine the cream's colour.

Odor : The cream's aroma was determined to be one of its distinguishing features.

State: The cream was visually inspected to determine its state.

Consistency: The formulation was tested by manually rubbing the cream on the hand.

pH: A digital pH meter was used to measure the cream's pH. The solution of cream was made by using 10 ml of distilled water and kept aside for 2 hours. For a solution, pH was measured 3 times and the average value was calculated.

- 2) *Spreadability*: By sandwiching the sample between 2 slides and compressing it to an even thickness for a redetermined amount of time, the spreadability of the cream was evaluated. The spreadability was calculated as the time needed to separate 2 slides. Better spreadability results in a shorter period.
- 3) *Washability*: After applying the formulation to the skin, the ease of water washing was evaluated.

- 4) *Non-irritancy test*: The non-irritancy test of the cream was assessed. The state was monitored for 24 hours.
- 5) *Phase separation*: Transferring the cream into a suitable wide-mouthed container. After 24 hours of storage, the oil phase and aqueous phase separation shouldn't be observed.
- 6) *After feeling*: After applying the predetermined amount of cream, the emollient's slipperiness and amount of residue were judged to be satisfactory.
- 7) *Dye solubility test*: This test involves mixing a tiny amount of cream with a water-soluble dye (methylene blue), which then is examined under a microscope. If the continuous phase appears blue, the emulsion is an O/W type because the external phase contains water and dye will dissolve in it to give color. If the continuous phase remains colourless and the scattered globules are blue, the cream is W/O type. The reciprocal is for an oil-soluble dye (Sudan III).
- 8) *Dilution test*: In this test, the cream is diluted either with oil or with water. The O/W type of cream will remain stable when diluted with water because water is the dispersion medium; but if diluted with oil will break because oil and water aren't miscible. While the vice versa is for a W/O type of emulsion.
- 9) *Cobalt chloride test*: This test involves soaking of Whatman filter strips in a cobalt chloride solution for 10 minutes. When the stripes dry, it turns blue. Results are seen after drying blue strips that had been soaked in sample cream for 5 minutes. If an O/W type of emulsion is present the blue cobalt chloride should turn pink.

Fig. 7 (a) parenchyma cells with starch:

- 10) *Antibacterial assay*: The “Agar Cup-Plate Method” was used to test the ant-bacterial efficacy of polyherbal anti-bacterial cream on diverse bacteria. To evaluate the antibacterial activity against 2 distinct bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* & *Escherichia coli* along with 4 Petri plates were used. Agar solution containing nutrients was placed on the plates and solidification was permitted. After that, the subculture's bacteria were put into nutrient agar media, which had 2 cavities already created. Standard cream was placed in 1st compartment while the sample was placed in 2nd compartment. The sample was made sure to be positioned at the cavity's level. The plates were checked for the development of an inhibitory zone after 24 hours. The antibacterial activity is measured from the zone of inhibition.

III. Results

To verify the authenticity of Neem, it was necessary to examine its epidermal cells, pericyclic cells, and calcium oxalate crystals. In examining the cinnamon powder starch grains, we made use of observations of the parenchyma cells for authentication. After utilizing the Soxhlet apparatus and alcohol as a solvent, we were successful in obtaining plant powder. We were pleased to discover that my efforts produced 11 ml of neem extract and 10 ml of cinnamon extract. Upon conducting a thorough phytochemical screening, the following outcomes were observed. Upon completion of the Cream formulation procedure and a meticulous evaluation of its various parameters, we have successfully generated a comprehensive table of results. Our rigorous analysis has conclusively determined that F2 Cream outperforms F1 Cream in terms of efficacy. Moving forward, we proceeded to conduct a rigorous anti-bacterial effectiveness test of F2 Cream against a commercially available cream (Cloben-G) utilizing the agar diffusion cup-plate method. The outcome of our testing was beyond impressive, with our product demonstrating significant anti-bacterial activity.

Fig. 6 Powder study of *Azadirachta indica* (A) Rosettes crystal (B) vessels with spiral thickness (c)pollen grain (D) trichomes

Table2: Phytochemical screening of extracts

Sr.No.	Chemical Constituents	Test	Result	
			Neem	Cinnamon
1	<i>Alkaloid</i>	Mayers test	+	+
		Wagner’s test	+	-
		Hager’s test	-	+
		Dragendroffs test	+	+
2	<i>Saponin</i>	Foam test	+	-
		Haemolytic test	-	-
		Bromine water test	+	-
		Legal’s test	+	-
3	<i>Triterpenoids</i>	Salkowski test	+	-
		Liebermann Burchard test	-	-
4	<i>Carbohydrates</i>	Molisch’s test	-	-
		Barfoed’s test	-	-
		Benedicts’ test	-	-
5	<i>Flavonoids</i>	Ferric chloride test	-	-
		Shinoda test	+	-
		Lead acetate test	+	-
6	<i>Amino acids</i>	Ninhydrin test	+	-
7	<i>Tannins</i>	Ferric Chloride test	-	-
		Lead acetate test	+	-

Fig. 8 Soxhlet apparatus with neem powder

Fig. 9 Formulating Cream in laboratory

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameters	Formulated Polyherbal Cream		Marketed Herbal Cream
		F1	F2	
1	Colour	Off - White		
2	Odour	Minty Rose		
3	Texture	Smooth		
4	Appearance And Homogeneity	Elegant & Excellent	Elegant & Excellent	Smooth & Good
5	Type Of Smear	Good		d
6	Skin Irritancy	Yes	Yes	No
7	pH	6.2	5.8	6.4
8	Dilution Test	O/W Emulsion Type	O/W Emulsion Type	O/W Emulsion Type
9	Dye Test	O/W Emulsion Type	O/W Emulsion Type	O/W Emulsion Type
10	Cobalt Chloride Test	O/W Emulsion Type	O/W Emulsion Type	O/W Emulsion Type
11	Stability Test	Stable	Stable	Stable

Fig. 10 Polyherbal Cream

Table 3: Evaluation

IV. Discussion

Our team has conducted research intending to create and test herbal skincare products that possess potent anti-bacterial properties. We are pleased to announce that our endeavors have resulted in the successful development of a cream that leverages a diverse array of herbal alcoholic extracts that are recognized for their ability to combat bacterial infections.

Our study encompasses a comprehensive description of the cream, an examination of existing literature, in-vitro anti-bacterial testing, and other relevant pharmaceutical evaluations. We have conducted extensive reviews of the literature to carefully select the herbs utilized in the cream, ensuring that they possess the necessary efficacy in fighting bacteria.

We are confident that our research and product development will contribute significantly to the field of skincare and provide consumers with a safer and more effective alternative to traditional anti-bacterial products.

The neem and cinnamon alcoholic extracts, along with nutmeg oil, make up the polyherbal cream in two different compositions, labeled F1 and F2. After undergoing thorough pharmaceutical evaluations, the optimal values for all parameters were determined. However, the F2 handwash gel outperformed the F1 handwash gel, and the polyherbal cream showed significant antibacterial efficacy during the antibacterial assay. We were motivated to create a polyherbal cream with anti-bacterial properties due to the increase in "Nosocomial disease" in our environment and the growing awareness among individuals of the advantages of using herbs instead of synthetic products available in the market. Herbal creams are superior to other creams because they not only efficiently fulfill their intended purpose, but they also do not cause any adverse reactions and

Fig. 11 Anti-bacterial assay of cream using (a) B. subtilis (b) E.coli

help maintain better skin texture. This prevents the skin from reacting negatively to synthetic products, such as developing rashes, dryness, or roughness.

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